

Synthesis of 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-Aryloxy-3-substituted-aminocyclohexan-2-ols as Potential Biodynamic Agents

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Epoxidation of 1-(phenoxy, *p*-acetamidophenoxy, *p*-propionylphenoxy and *p*- α -hydroxyethylphenoxy)-2-cyclohexenes (6-9), prepared from phenols (1-4) and 1-chloro-2-cyclohexene (5), with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid gave a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-1-aryloxy-2,3-epoxycyclohexanes (10-13) and also a Baeyer-Villiger oxidation product, -(*p*-propionylphenoxy)-2,3-epoxycyclohexane (12c). Condensation of 10-13 and *trans*-1-phenoxy-2,3-epoxycyclopentane (33), obtained from 1-phenoxy-2-cyclopentene (32), with appropriate amines furnished the desired 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-aryloxy-3-substituted-aminocyclohexan-2-ols (14-28 and 34). Acetylation of 1-phenoxy-3-*N*'-phenylpiperazinylcyclohexan-2-ol (14) afforded its 2-acetoxy derivative (29) and hydrolysis of 1-(*p*-acetamidophenoxy)-3-isopropylaminocyclohexan-2-ol (25) gave the *p*-aminophenoxy compound (31). Treatment of 29 with EtCOCl-AlCl₃ afforded 1-(*p*-propionylphenoxy)-2-acetoxy derivative (30) which on hydrolysis furnished its 2-hydroxy compound 28. Only compounds 18 and 25 showed anti-arrhythmic and β -adrenoceptor blocking activities, respectively, while no other compound exhibited any significant pharmacological activities.

1-Aryloxy-3-substituted-aminopropan-2-ols (I) possess wide variety of biological activities¹⁻¹⁰ which were found to modulate by the nature of both aryloxy and amine moiety. The investigations undertaken so far, on these compounds, do not indicate the relationship of spatial orientation of aryloxy, amino and hydroxy components *versus* biological activity. Therefore, it appeared interesting to study such compounds in a semi-rigid structures having defined stereochemistry of aryloxy, amino and hydroxy moieties. In this direction, we report the synthesis and screening results of 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-aryloxy-3-substituted-aminocyclohexan-2-ols (II, 14-31).

(I)

(II)

1-(Phenoxy, *p*-acetamidophenoxy, *p*-propionylphenoxy and *p*- α -hydroxyethylphenoxy)-2-cyclohexenes (6-9) were prepared by the reaction of phenol (1), *p*-acetamidophenol (2), *p*-propionylphenoxy (3) and *p*- α -hydroxyethylphenol (4) with 1-chloro-2-cyclohexene (5) in aqueous NaOH-DMF. Epoxidation of 6-9 with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid gave corresponding epoxy compounds as a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-1-aryloxy-2,3-epoxycyclohexanes (10-13). In case of *p*-propionyl compound (8), the epoxidation resulted, besides an epoxide mixture, a Baeyer-Villiger oxidation product as a mixture of *cis*-/*trans*-1-(*p*-propionylphenoxy)-2,3-epoxycyclohexanes (12c). The epoxide mixture 10a, b was separated on silica gel column

to give *trans*-epoxide 10a, δ (CDCl₃) 3.26 (2H, bs, W/2 3 Hz, CH-CH) and 4.56 (1H, dt, *J* 2 and 7 Hz, CHOPh), and *cis*-epoxide 10b, δ (CDCl₃) 3.0-3.36

(2H, m, CH-CH) and 4.5 (1H, dt, *J* 2 and 7 Hz, CHOPh), in the proportion of 85 : 15. Other *cis*-/*trans*-epoxide mixtures were also found to contain mainly *trans*-epoxide 85-90% with 10-15% *cis*-epoxide.

Similarly, 1-phenoxy-2,3-epoxycyclopentanes (33a, b) were prepared from 1-phenoxy-2-cyclopentene (32) in the proportion of 60 : 40 which were

separated on silica gel column to give *trans*-epoxide

33a, δ (CDCl₃) 3.43 (2H, bs, CH-CH) and 4.6-4.8 (1H, m, CHOPh), and *cis*-epoxide 33b, δ (CDCl₃)

3.16-3.6 (2H, 2d, *J* 2.5 Hz, CH-CH) and 4.62 (1H, bt, *J* 2 and 5.5 Hz, CHOPh).

Theoretically condensation of such mixture of epoxides with nucleophiles is likely to yield four products¹¹, two due to *cis*-/*trans*-isomers and two by regional attack of nucleophile at C-2 and C-3 epoxide carbons. However, condensation of epoxide mixture 10a, b as well as of pure *trans*-epoxide 10a

Scheme 1

with *N*⁴-phenylpiperazine gave the same 1-phenoxy-3-*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinylcyclohexan-2-ol (**14**) on work-up and purification. In the pmr of **14**, C₂H proton appeared as a triplet at δ 3.64, *J* 9 Hz, which suggests a 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-stereochemistry. In this condensation, the minor product formed by the reaction of *cis*-epoxide **10b** and *N*-phenylpiperazine gets eliminated during work-up and purification. No effort was made to purify this minor product. Regarding other products corresponding to attack at C-2 carbon, no indication could be had from the nmr of crude product. It appears that due to steric interference at C-2 carbon by 1-aryloxy group, other products are produced in traces if at all are formed.

Thus, the desired 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-aryloxy-3-substituted-aminocyclohexan-2-ols (**II**, **14-28**) and 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-phenoxy-3-*N*⁴-(*p*-tolylpiperazinyl)cyclohexan-2-ol (**34**) were prepared by the condensation of epoxides **10-13** with appropriate amines. Condensation of **12a, b, c** with *N*-phenylpiperazine yielded a mixture of products corresponding to both *cis*/*trans*-epoxides **12a, b** and *cis*/*trans*-epoxides **12c**, which could only be separated by hydrolysis of the crude mixture by aqueous NaOH to obtain Baeyer-Villiger derived product and required 1-(*p*-propionylphenoxy)-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexan-2-ol (**28**) in low yield. To

circumvent these problems, an alternative method to prepare **28** was undertaken. Direct acylation of 1-phenoxy-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexan-2-ol (**14**) with propionic acid-PPA gave only the starting material. So, **14** was acetylated with Ac₂O-pyridine to give the corresponding 2-acetoxy derivative **29**. Friedel-Craft acylation of **29** with EtCOCl-AlCl₃ in CS₂ yielded 1-(*p*-propionylphenoxy) derivative (**30**) which on hydrolysis furnished the desired product **28**. Hydrolysis of 1-(*p*-acetamidophenoxy) compound **25** afforded 1-(*p*-aminophenoxy)-3-isopropylaminocyclohexan-2-ol (**31**).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in an electrically heated apparatus (Townson and Mercer Ltd., England) and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer 137 infracord, Perkin-Elmer 337 grating or Perkin-Elmer 177 grating instruments either as KBr films or as neat and frequencies. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal reference. Homogeneity of compounds was checked by tlc either on silica gel or on alumina plates. Analyses of the elements were found within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the calculated values.

The following experimental procedures are illustrative of the general methods employed to prepare various compounds described in Tables 1 and 2.

The synthesis of 1-chloro-2-cyclohexene¹³ (5), 1-chloro-2-cyclopentene¹³, 1-phenoxy-2-cyclohexene¹⁴ (6) and 1-phenoxy-2-cyclopentene¹⁴ (32) was carried out by reported methods as well as by the methods illustrated below for similar compounds.

1-(p-Acetamidophenoxy)-2-cyclohexene (7) : To a stirred and cooled (5°) mixture of NaOH (0.8 g,

20 mmol) in water (2 ml) and *p*-acetamidophenol (3.0 g, 20 mmol) in DMF (18 ml) was added 1-chloro-2-cyclohexene (2.3 g, 20 mmol) in DMF (18 ml) dropwise during 30 min. Stirring was continued for 2 h, during which temperature was allowed to come to room temperature and stirred for 0.5 h at this temperature and then left overnight in fridge. It was diluted with water (60 ml) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The extract washed thrice with 5% NaOH solution, water, saturated NaCl solution and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent furnished the required alkene 7, (3.0 g, 76%), m.p. 100° (benzene-hexane).

TABLE 1—1-ARYLOXY-2-CYCLO(HEXENES AND PENTENE) (6-9, 32) AND 1-ARYLOXY-2,3-EPOXYCYCLOHEXANES (10-13, 33)

Compd. ^a no.	R	Yield %	M.p. or b.p. ^b °C	Analysis ^c	δ ^d
6	H	79	140-142 at 3.5 mm	OH	1.9-2.3 (6H, bm, (OH ₂) ₂), 4.75 (1H, m, W/2 12 Hz, OHOPh), 5.85 (2H, bs, CH=CH)
7	<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	76	100	OHN	1.95 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 4.52 (1H, h, W/2 9 Hz, ArOCH), 5.7 (2H, bs, CH=CH), 8.5 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O exchangeable)
8	<i>p</i> -COOH, OH	57	197 at 3-4 mm	OH	1.16 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.05 (2H, q, J 7.5 Hz, COCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.60-5.0 (1H, bh, ArOCH), 5.86 (2H, bs, CH=CH), 6.83 (2H, dd, J 2 and 9 Hz, ArH <i>o</i> to O), 7.83 (2H, dd, J 2 and 9 Hz, ArH <i>o</i> to CO)
9	<i>p</i> -OH(OH)C ₂ H ₅	60	160 at 0.1 mm	OH	0.84 (3H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (1H, h, OH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 4.46 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, CH(OH)Et), 5.9 (2H, bs, CH=CH), 4.76 (1H, h, W/2 10 Hz, OHOPh)
32	H	64	92-98 at 2 mm	OH	1.6-2.5 (4H, m, (OH ₂) ₂), 3.55-3.92 (1H, bh, OHOPh), 5.92 (2H, bs, CH=CH)
10a (<i>trans</i>)	H		134 at 3.5 mm	OH	1.5-2.4 (6H, bm, (OH ₂) ₂), 3.26 (2H, bs, W/2 3 Hz, CH-CH), 4.56 (1H, dt, J 2 and 7 Hz, OHOPh)
10b (<i>cis</i>)	H		Oil	OH	1.0-2.3 (6H, bm, (OH ₂) ₂), 3.0-3.36 (2H, m, CH-CH), 4.5 (1H, dt, J 2 and 7 Hz, OHOPh)
11	<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	54	76	OHN	2.1 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.18 (2H, bs, CH-CH), 4.20- 4.65 (1H, bt, OHOPh), 8.26 (1H, h, NHCO, D ₂ O exchangeable)
12a,b+ 12c	<i>p</i> -COEt+ <i>p</i> -OCOEt		Oil	OH	1.18-1.25 (3H, two t, J 7 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.1-2.3 (6H, bm, (OH ₂) ₂), 2.56 and 2.92 (2H, two q, J 7 Hz, COCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.18 (2H, bs, CH-CH), 4.32-4.8 (1H, m, OHOPh), 6.82-7.16 (ArH, m, <i>o</i> to O) Distribution of ArH at two chemical shifts was in the ratio of 3 : 5.6, 7.85 (ArH, dd, J 2.5 and 9 Hz, <i>o</i> to CO)
13	<i>p</i> -OH(OH)Et		Oil	OH	0.9 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.16-2.16 (8H, bm, (OH ₂) ₂ and CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.2 (3H, bs, CH-CH, OH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 4.53 (2H, bt, OHOPh and CHOH)
33a (<i>trans</i>)	H		80-90 at 0.4 mm (of mix.)	OH	1.4-2.3 (4H, m, (OH ₂) ₂), 3.43 (2H, s, CH-CH), 4.6-4.8 (1H, m, OHOPh)
33b (<i>cis</i>)	H			OH	1.1-2.3 (4H, m, (OH ₂) ₂), 3.16-3.6 (2H, two d, J-2.5 Hz, CH-CH), 4.62 (bt, J 2 and 5.5 Hz, CHOPh)

^a Described in Scheme and stereochemistry as indicated. ^b Free bases crystallised from benzene-hexane and oily compounds purified on silica column. ^c Elemental analyses found within ±0.4% of theoretical values. Structures characterised on the basis of nmr data. ^d Unless otherwise stated nmr recorded in CDCl₃ on Varian A 60D or R-32; data described which have direct bearing on structure, and details of ArH avoided.

TABLE 2—1-ARYLOXY-3-SUBSTITUTED-AMINOCYCLO(HEXANES AND PENTANE) (14-31, 34)

Compd ^a no.	N and (R)	Yield %	M.p. ^b °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) ^c			ALD ₅₀ ^d	Noteworthy activity ^e
					O	H	N		
14	N ⁴ -Phenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	80	106 (B) 229 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	62.00 (62.12)	7.28 (7.10)	6.80 (6.70)	800	Depressant AI 61 (160 p.o.) AA 25
15	N ⁴ - <i>m</i> -Methoxy- phenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	78	109 (B) 231 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	60.30 (60.65)	7.70 (7.03)	6.03 (6.15)	200	AA 25
16	N ⁴ - <i>o</i> -Methoxy- phenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	67	95 (B) 257 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	59.50 (60.65)	7.30 (7.03)	5.71 (6.15)	—	—
17	N ⁴ - <i>o</i> -Methyl- phenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	77	122 (B) 290 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	6.10 (6.40)	—	—
18	N ⁴ - <i>p</i> -Methyl- phenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	74	135 (B) 255 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	6.18 (6.40)	400	Depressant AA 17
19	N ⁴ -3,4-Di- methylphenyl- piperazinyl (R=H)	66	115 (B) 150 (H)	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	—	—	5.82 (6.18)	800	Depressant
20	Morpholinyl (R=H)	86	62 (B) 245 (H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂	69.50 (69.40)	8.40 (8.34)	4.99 (5.00)	300	AA 11
21	4-Hydroxy-4- phenyl- piperidyl (R=H)	68	105 (B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ NO ₂	75.20 (75.20)	8.95 (7.95)	4.19 (3.81)	800	—
22	<i>t</i> -Butylamino (R=H)	66	70 (B) 242 (H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ NO ₂ Cl	64.46 (64.10)	8.55 (8.67)	4.62 (4.67)	300	—
23	Isopropyl- amino (R=H)	77	80 (B) 245 (H)	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ NO ₂ Cl	—	—	4.59 (4.90)	—	—
24	3,4-Dimethoxy- phenylethyl- amino (R=H)	68	106 (B) 181 (H)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ NO ₂ Cl	—	—	3.56 (3.44)	300	—
25	Isopropyl- amino (R=NHCOMe)	80	125 (B) 106 (H)	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	66.70 (66.66)	8.40 (8.50)	8.89 (9.15)	800	β-blocking activity
26	<i>t</i> -Butylamino (R=NHCOMe)	69	140 (B) 264 (H)	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	60.53 (60.58)	8.20 (8.13)	7.82 (7.85)	—	—
27	3,4-Dimethoxy- phenylethyl- amino (R=NHCOMe)	73	130 (B) 164 (H)	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂	67.40 (67.29)	7.40 (7.47)	6.55 (6.54)	—	—
28	N ⁴ -Phenyl- piperazinyl (R=COEt)	57	128 (B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	—	—	7.19 (6.86)	—	—
29	—	73	98 (B)	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂	—	—	7.30 (7.11)	—	—
30	—	70	188 (B)	C ₂₇ H ₃₄ N ₂ O ₂	—	—	6.05 (6.22)	—	—
31	—	80	133 (H)	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	60.10 (59.90)	8.30 (8.32)	9.30 (9.33)	—	—
34	—	50	131 (B)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	74.68 (75.00)	8.12 (7.95)	7.80 (7.95)	—	—

^a Described in Scheme; structures of 29-31, 34 described complete in Scheme; synthesised by the general methods described in Experimental. ^b Free base (B) crystallised from benzene-hexane and hydrochloride (H) from MeOH-Et₂O. ^c Elemental analyses found within ±0.4% is described/included in Table. ^d Approximate LD₅₀. ^e Depressant implies reduced motor activity, ataxia, loss of righting reflex; AI=antiinflammatory activity; numbers describe the percent inhibition of carrageenin induced oedema in mice at a dose of 0.2 ALD₅₀; AA=antiarrhythmic activity on isolated guinea-pig auricle, f_{max}ures describe the percentage decrease in maximal driving frequency at 3 × 10⁻⁶ g ml⁻¹.

Similarly, 1-(phenoxy, *p*-propionylphenoxy and *p*-α-hydroxyethylphenoxy)-2-cyclohexenes (6-9) were prepared and characteristic data of 6-9 are described in Table 1.

1-(*p*-Acetamidophenoxy)-2,3-epoxycyclohexane (11): *m*-Chloroperbenzoic acid (10 g, 27 mmol) in dioxane (100 ml) was added to a solution of 7 (1.0 g, 25 mmol) in dioxane (40 ml) cooled to 15°

during 30 min. The mixture was stirred for 1 h during which temperature was allowed to come to room temperature, left in fridge for 4 days and then 24 h at 25-30°. The precipitated solid was dissolved in 10% KOH solution, the organic layer extracted with CH_2Cl_2 , and extract washed with 10% KOH solution, water, saturated NaCl solution, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to yield epoxy product **11** (8.0 g), m.p. 110°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 233 (NH), 1 662 (C=O) and 834 cm^{-1} (oxirane).

Similarly, 1-(phenoxy, *p*-propionylphenoxy and *p*- α -hydroxyethylphenoxy)-2,3-epoxycyclohexanes (**10**, **12** and **13**) were prepared as a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-epoxides in around 10-15% as *cis*- and 85-90% as *trans*-epoxides. The mixture of epoxides **10a**, **b** was separated on silica gel or neutral alumina column using hexane, benzene-hexane (1:1), and benzene as eluant. The fractions were monitored on silica gel tlc plates. The former fractions were found to contain *trans*-epoxide **10a** and the later elutions gave *cis*-epoxide **10b**. The characterisation data of various epoxides prepared are described in Table 1.

In case of alkene **8**, epoxidation accompanied with Baeyer-Villiger oxidation also to yield a mixture of expected *cis*/*trans*-epoxide **12a**, **b** along with 1-(*p*-propionylphenoxy)-2,3-epoxy-cyclohexane (**12c**) as a mixture of *cis*/*trans*-epoxide.

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-Phenoxy-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexane-2-ol (14**)**: A solution of *trans*-epoxide (**10a**) (0.3 g, 1.6 mmol) and *N*-phenylpiperazine (0.16 g, 1.6 mmol) in ethanol was refluxed for 3 h on steam-bath. The solvent was removed by distillation and the residue triturated with benzene-hexane to give **14** (0.3 g, 75%), m.p. 106° (benzene-hexane); hydrochloride, m.p. 229° (MeOH-Et₂O); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 348 (OH) cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.0-2.4 (6H, bm, $(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 2.4-3.04 (5H, m, $\text{CHN}(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 3.0-3.42 (4H, m, $\text{PhN}(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 3.64 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, *CHOH*), 4.58-5.05 (1H, bh, *CHOPh*) and 6.7-7.5 (10H, m, *ArH*).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-(*p*-Acetamidophenoxy)-3-*t*-butylaminocyclohexane (26**)**: A solution of **11** (0.25 g, 1 mmol) and excess of *t*-butylamine (0.3 g) in methanol was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated to dryness and the residue was crystallised from benzene-hexane to afford **26** (0.2 g, 69%), m.p. 140°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 250 (NH and OH) cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.13 (9H, s, $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$), 1.21-2.03 (6H, m, $(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 2.1 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.58 (2H, h, *OH* and *NH*, D_2O exchangeable), 3.25 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz, *CHOH*, and *J* 2 and 8.5 Hz, *CHNH*), 3.66-4.33 (1H, bh, *CHOPh*) 6.66-7.5 (4H, m, *ArH*) and 7.5-7.76 (1H, bm, NHCOCH_3).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-Phenoxy-2-acetoxy-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexane-2-ol (29**)**: Refluxing **14** (2.0 g) with Ac_2O (5 ml) for 2.5 h or treatment of **14** with Ac_2O -pyridine followed by removal of excess Ac_2O *in vacuo* gave residue which was suspended in water and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The extract was washed with 5% NaHCO_3 solution,

water saturated NaCl solution and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of CH_2Cl_2 by distillation followed by evacuation gave **29** (0.8 g, 73%), m.p. 98°; δ (CDCl_3) 0.35-1.8 (6H, bm, $(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 1.8 (3H, s, COCH_3), 1.9-2.9 (5H, m, $\text{CHN}(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 2.9-3.3 (4H, m, $\text{PhN}(\text{CH}_2)_6$), 3.8-4.43 (1H, bh, *CHOPh*), 5.08 (1H, t, *J* 9.5 Hz, *CHOAc*).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-(*p*-Propionylphenoxy)-2-acetoxy-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexane (30**)**: A solution of **29** (1.06 g, 2.7 mmol) and EtCOCl (1.2 g, 10 mmol) in CS_2 was added all at once to a vigorously stirred suspension of AlCl_3 (1.2 g) in CS_2 (30 ml) at 15°. The mixture was allowed to come to room temperature and stirred further for 15-20 min. Then it was refluxed for 5 h, CS_2 distilled off and complex decomposed with dilute HCl. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from MeOH-Et₂O to give **30** as hydrochloride (1.0 g, 70%), m.p. 188°; δ (CDCl_3) 1.11 (3H, t, COCH_2CH_3), 1.76 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.0-4.5 (1H, bh, *CHOPh*), 4.82-5.26 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, *CHOAc*).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-(*p*-Propionylphenoxy)-3-(*N*⁴-phenylpiperazinyl)cyclohexan-2-ol (28**)**: Refluxing of **30** (0.3 g) in 4% methanolic KOH for 3 h followed by concentration, dilution with water and filtration of the solid gave **28** (150 mg, 57%) m.p. 128° (hexane); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 652 (C=O) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (OH); δ (CDCl_3) 1.10 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 3.5 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, *CHOH*), 3.7-4.5 (1H, bh, *CHOPh*), 3.85 (1H, h, *OH*, D_2O exchangeable), 6.4-7.4 (7H, m, *ArH* of C_6H_5 and *o* to *O*) and 7.8 (2H, dd, *J* 2 and 9 Hz, *ArH* *o* to *CO*).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-(*p*-Aminophenoxy)-3-isopropylaminocyclohexan-2-ol (31**)**: 1-(*p*-Acetamidophenoxy)-3-isopropylaminocyclohexan-2-ol (**25**) hydrochloride (0.2 g) was refluxed with 6*N* HCl (1 ml) for 2 h. Concentration and trituration with dry Et₂O afforded **31** (150 mg, 80%), m.p. 133°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 460 cm^{-1} (NH_2).

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-Phenoxy-3-(*N*⁴-*p*-methylphenylpiperazinyl)cyclopentan-2-ol (34**)**: *trans*-1-Phenoxy-2,3-epoxycyclopentane (**33**; 0.21 g, 1.2 mmol) and *p*-methylphenylpiperazine (0.21 g, 1.2 mmol) in methanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. It was concentrated, diluted with water and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 . The extract washed with water, saturated NaCl solution and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of methylene chloride gave **34** (100 mg), m.p. 131° (benzene-hexane).

Pharmacological activity: The approximate lethal dose (ALD_{50}) in 50% of animals and gross behavioural effects were studied in mice by intraperitoneal administration of graded doses of compounds using five animals at each dose level. The effect on blood pressure and respiration and interaction with acetylcholine and epinephrine on these parameters were studied in anaesthetised (phenobarbitone, 35 mg/kg) cats.

The *in vitro* antiarrhythmic activity of these compounds was tested by the method of Dawes¹⁵ in

TABLE 3— β -BLOCKING ACTIVITY OF COMPOUND 25

Compd. no.	Dose mg/kg	Isolated guinea-pig ileum			Isoprenaline induced hypotension and tachycardia ^a	
		Anti-acetylcholine %	Anti-histamine %	Anti-5-HT %	Blood pressure % block	Heart rate % block
25	1.0	63	↑ 80	↑ 18	20	50

^a In repeated experiments at this dose and higher doses the response varies considerably, possibly due to variable absorption. ↑ ≡ Potentiation.

TABLE 4—ANTIARRHYTHMIC ACTIVITY OF COMPOUND 18

Compd. no.	Ventricular fibrillation threshold in cats		Cardiotonic effect of ouabin in guinea-pigs pre-treated with 18 (40 mg/kg i.v.) ^a			
	Dose mg/kg i.v.	% Increase in threshold voltage	Treatment	EA ^b	VFT ^c	CA ^d
18	2.0	60	18	13.7	17.8	23.1
Quinidine	5.0	58	Saline	14.2	19.5	23.4

Values are mean of ouabin ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g}$) required for the on-set of EA, VFT, CA. ^a EA ≡ Early arrhythmia. ^b VFT ≡ Ventricular fibrillation threshold. ^c CA ≡ Cardiac arrest.

isolated guinea-pig auricle and the effect was compared with a 3×10^{-5} g/ml concentration of quinidine. Interaction of the compounds with histamine and acetylcholine was studied on isolated guinea-pig ileum.

The *in vivo* antiarrhythmic activity of these compounds was studied in anaesthetised (urethane, 1 g/kg, i.p.) rats (150-300 g) and guinea-pigs (400-650 g) of either sex. The jugular vein was cannulated for infusion of aconitine (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; 4.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{min}$) in rats and ouabin (62.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; 3.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{min}$) in guinea-pigs by slow injection apparatus. The ECG (Lead II) changes were monitored and recorded on encardiorite polygraph before and after the administration of test compounds and during the infusion of ouabin. The test compounds were injected 2 min before starting the infusion. Quinidine was used as the amount of aconitine or ouabin required for the onset of early arrhythmia (EA), ventricular fibrillation (VF) and cardiac arrest (CA) per 100 g of body weight.

β -Adrenergic blocking activity was determined from antagonism of isoprenaline induced vaso-depressor response in anaesthetised cats and relaxation of isolated guinea-pig tracheal chain. Those compounds which showed β -adrenergic receptor blocking activity in these tests were then evaluated for their antiarrhythmic activity against electrically induced arrhythmias in isolated guinea-pig auricles, against ouabin induced arrhythmias in guinea-pigs and against isoprenaline inhibition of acetylcholine or histamine induced bronchospasm in anaesthetised guinea-pigs^{1,6}.

The pharmacological screening results of compounds tested by the above methods are described in Tables 2-4 and discussed below.

1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-Phenoxy-3-(*N*⁴-(phenyl, *p*-methylphenyl, 3,4-dimethylphenyl)piperazinyl)cyclohexan-2-ols (14, 18 and 19) showed CNS depressant activity and compounds 14, 18, 3-*N*⁴-*m*-methoxyphenylpiperazinyl (15) and 3-morpholinyl (20) exhibited interesting antiarrhythmic activity. 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-(*p*-Acetamidophenoxy)-3-isopropylamino-cyclohexan-2-ol (25) possesses significant β -adrenoceptor blocking activity but much weaker than the acyclic prototype drug Practolol. The detailed activity data of active compounds 18 and 25 are described in Tables 3 and 4. Of the four active compounds, only 18 showed marked antiarrhythmic activity which compares well with the reference compound (quinidine, Table 4) in ventricular fibrillation threshold in cats and cardiotonic effect of ouabin in guinea-pigs, EA, VFT, and CA. As structural modifications carried out in the present study were not according to a particular activity, so no structure-activity relationship could be drawn up. Other stereoisomers need to be studied for meaningful inferences, regarding role of spatial disposition of aryloxy, hydroxy and amino moieties in contributing particular biological response. On the basis of the present study, it may be suggested that such 1,2-*trans*-2,3-*trans*-1-aryloxy-3-substituted-aminocyclohexan-2-ols (II) are potential biodynamic agents as well as useful probes to provide information of stereochemistry of 1-aryloxy-3-substituted-aminopropan-2-ols (I) eliciting biological response.

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